

Online Comedy Skits as Guarantee for Freedom of Expression in a Digital Age

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Abstract

The researchers examined the role of comedy skits and other forms of online media in protecting freedom of expression in Nigeria in the digital era. The objectives were to interrogate the extent to which online comedy skits enhance freedom of expression in the film industry and to ascertain the relationship between extent of freedom of expression in Nigeria and extent of freedom enjoyed by Nigerian online comedy skit makers. The researchers adopted survey research method and questionnaire as the measuring instrument. A total of 400 respondents were purposively selected for this exercise using snowball sampling technique to ensure that only the right respondents attended to the questionnaire. The results showed that Nigeria's political and social climate often restricts freedom of expression, particularly for those who critique the government or societal norms; thus, 55.3% believe that safety of media workers and social media skit makers are not guaranteed. However, 55.5% and 24% strongly agree and agree respectively that online comedy skit makers are not restrictive in their choice of language or fashion style, signaling the possibility of abuse and cyber bullying. The data also revealed that 64% of the respondents strongly believe that, through jokes online comedy skit makers are able to draw attention to salient issues in the society. Based on the findings, the researchers recommended the promotion of public awareness of the importance of creative freedom in the film industry and the dangers of government censorship.

Keywords: Online, Comedy, Skits, Freedom, Expression, Film, Regulations

Introduction

Online comedy skits have emerged as a powerful medium for the exercise of freedom of expression in Nigeria. In a country where traditional media often faces censorship and restrictions, digital platforms have provided comedians with an unprecedented avenue to express their views and critique societal norms. This is particularly significant as humour allows for the discussion of sensitive topics while engaging a wide audience. Moreover,

the digital nature of these skits enables comedians to reach a global audience, fostering a sense of solidarity among Nigerians on socio-political issues. It creates an open dialogue where individuals can discuss issues without fear of repression.

Nigerian comedians, like Mark Angel, Taaoma, Trinity, YanBaba, Bovi, Broda Shaggi, Lasisi Elenu, Basket Mouth, Officer Woos, employ satire and humor to address pressing issues such as corruption, politics, and social inequalities. These skits often incorporate clever commentary, serving as a form of social criticism while invoking laughter. The widespread accessibility of these skits on social media platforms ensures that messages reach a broad and diverse audience, transcending geographical and socio-economic boundaries.

The past 70 years has witnessed the metamorphosis of comedy from an art or entertainment performed entirely to live audiences to a form also disseminated by mass media and now, in particular, by social media (Sturges, 2015). The social media have widened the frontiers of the media landscape, providing unfettered access to contents that would have otherwise been banned or censored by the authorities. The implication for a country like Nigeria with poor history of press freedom is germane. Nigeria was ranked 120 out of 180 countries in the 2021 world press freedom index by Reporters without Borders, a drop of five spots from the 2020 ranking. In 2022, Lungile Dumisani (2022) reports that it has sunk deeper to 129. This signals a poor appreciation of press freedom and freedom of expression in Nigeria. Dumisani, further quotes Reporters Without Borders as revealing that Nigeria is “one of West Africa’s most dangerous and difficult countries for journalists, who are often watched, attacked, arbitrarily arrested and even killed...It can involve pressure, harassment of journalists and media outlets, and even censorship.

For Nigerian social media content creators, especially known comedy skit makers who satirise government and negative trends in society, freedom of expression is not without challenges. Comedians often face backlash, threats, and even legal action for their content. The Nigerian government's attempts to regulate online content have raised concerns about censorship. Abuse of the cyber space, misinformation, fake news, terrorism and cyber bullying are some of the reasons governments adduce for wanting to regulate citizens’ social media engagements. Ogbuoshi, Oyeleke & Folorunsho (2019, p. 47) argue that “not only has hate speeches pitched the north against the south, but individual hatred has attained an all-time height in Nigeria.” Also Santas & Inobemhe (2021, p.72) argue that “social media have been identified as platforms that aid terrorism and encourage insecurity across different territories.” In, Anderson & Rainie (2020) in what they describe as ‘techlash’ describe recent incidents where users exploit the advantages of the social media for the wrong reasons.

No doubt, any freedom without safeguards is bound to be abused. Santas & Inobemhe (2021, p.73) citing Chakrabarti (2018) explain that “social media is giving people the platform to have a voice in government – providing the space for citizens to discuss issues, organise themselves for a common purpose and hold leaders accountable.”

Giving voice to the voiceless majority in a democratic society, thus, deepening democracy remains a formidable reason for its existence. However, false alarm, foreign interference, defamation of character, publication of obscenities, sexualisation of contents and political harassment are also issues witnessed in the social media which bothers the government. Governments worry that online platforms are providing too much powers to the citizens (Howard, 2011). For instance, on why he does not engage in social media, the current Nigerian president, Ahmed Bola Tinubu, during the campaign period alleged that he develops high blood pressure anytime he gets exposed to the social media. According to him, the reason is that, “people insult the hell out of me”. Some of the issues people complain about appear as comic strips that parody politicians and satirize events in the society.

Police extortion, bribery and corruption in government, Presidents Buhari and Tinubu certificate saga and Buhari’s “I’m not aware” response to questions about malfeasance under his watch, the idea of animals swallowing money, and lopsided fight against corruption that targets only opposition political party members were issues satirised by online comedians which the mainstream media would not have allowed. Others include rigging of the 2023 presidential election in favour of the ruling party and the judicial interpretation of the law. These and many more made the Nigerian government unpopular. The implication is the ban on Twitter, and proposal of bills to control social media activities by citizens. Protection from Internet Falsehood and Manipulation Bill 2019 was proposed in the Senate (Ewang, 2019), while a bill to establish the Independent National Commission for the Prohibition of Hate Speech Bill was proposed in 2020 (Ayeni, 2020). Both bills are seen to target free speech, and to punish social media users for being able to express themselves –the hate speech bill proposes the maximum penalty of death for offenders, (Amnesty International, 2019a, cited in Santas & Inobemhe 2021).

Nevertheless, the resilience of comedians and their ability to navigate these challenges underscore the importance of online comedy skits as a guarantee for freedom of expression in Nigeria. They serve as a vibrant reflection of the country's democratic spirit, pushing boundaries and challenging the status quo while bringing much-needed humor to complex societal issues. However, there is no existing literature on the contributions of online skits to freedom of speech in Nigeria, nor the perception of it by Nigerians. This study, therefore, examined the perception of online comedy skits as a guarantee for freedom of expression.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Find out the extent to which online comedy skits enhance freedom of expression in the film industry.

2. Interrogate the relationship between extent of freedom of expression in Nigeria and extent of freedom enjoyed by Nigerian online comedy skit makers.

Literature Review

The concept of freedom of expression means different things to different societies and cultures. Scholars who bare their minds on the concept of freedom of expression draw inspiration from the propositions made by John Stuart Mill (1806 – 1873) who popularised the well-known Libertarian theory of the press (Richard, 2019; Forte, 2022; Alfina *et al* 2023). According to Forte (2022):

There is a general agreement that speech rights as we have them today first emerged in a somewhat recognisable form with the rise of Liberalism People could not be trusted with the freedom to speak their minds because the exercise of such a freedom has the potential to upset the social structures which undermine the society.

In his view, the concept of freedom of expression should have limits within the boundary of the law of the land. The rational nature of man makes it dangerous to allow freedom of expression without some form of restriction to make individuals take responsibilities for what they say. Other scholars believe that freedom of expression is subsumed in the freedom of the press.

A free press is not necessarily a system where provision is made for freedom but one in which there are guarantees or safeguards to prevent abuse. The term freedom is relative to every society. The nature of the freedom enjoyed by the communist press might be considered repressive by western standards. Every press system enjoys a measure of freedom. However, the kind of freedom each enjoys is determined by the nature of the society itself (Ndolo, 2005). If for instance, the society is free; its press will be free. But in a closed system life is methodical and regimented and so is its press. Nigeria operates an admixture of free and closed economies that's why it is almost difficult to say whether there is freedom of expression in the right sense of it in the country because there are certain issues that individuals do not want to comment on and if they do, they might not necessarily do it the way it is given the kind of threat from the powers that be in the society.

Although, there is no absolute freedom anywhere in the world, especially that of the press, but then Nigerian constitution should promulgate a special right of the press and not generalised as stated by Yalaju (2006, p. 91) that section 39(1) of the 1999 Constitution of Nigeria right of freedom of expansion and the press states, "every person shall be entitled to freedom of expression, including freedom to hold opinion and receive and impact ideas and information without interference." The seeming freedom of the press is guaranteed by statements of general principle as commonly expressed in the constitution of democratic countries. In Nigeria, the freedom has not been free as the word implies – able to act at will, not under compulsion or restrain, independent, not

restricted. In spite of the constitutional guarantee the press has not been free in Nigeria. This has made (democracy) life difficult, specifically during military governments.

Unlike Nigeria, the United States of America is the freest press in the world, the independence of their press and by extension that of the individual is guaranteed by the first amendment which is very and reliable to enable the journalists win, during litigation. This fact did not deny the citizen their other rights when a journalist goes contrary in terms of libel invasion of privacy and trespass;. Although, libel varies from State to State, none inhibit the press from reporting the truth. If Nigeria wants to emulate democratic system of government from America why not the full Freedom of the Press and Information Act which are evidence of a democratic set up, why overlook the most important aspect of the democracy?

Citing the content of the constitution of Sweden, Carlsson & Weibull (2018) explained that freedom of expression is not unconditional. They added that the fundamental laws of the land provide that the freedom may be limited for reasons of national security, to maintain public order and safety, to protect individuals' good repute and right to privacy and to prevent crime and bring criminals to justice (p.11). From the words of John Stuart Mill, freedom of expression could help individuals refine their ideas, yet it was no panacea. Studies have shown that there was simply no guarantee that, even in the long term, progressive ideas would triumph over reactionary institutions – which according to Mill, included dissenting voices to the voice of reason (Alfina *et al* 2023).

Scholars have argued that freedom of expression meant well for the common good of individuals but it should have some restrictions within the boundaries of the laws of the land. This according to them makes individuals responsible of their actions and also guide against derogatory statements made against public office holders (Richard, 2019 and Alfina *et al* 2023). According to Alfina *et al* (2023): Freedom of expression is considered important because of these four reasons:

- a. To ensure one's self-fulfilment and also to reach one's maximum potential.
- b. To advance the search for truth and the advancement of knowledge or in their words "one who seeks knowledge and truth must hear all sides of the questions, consider all alternatives, tests its judgment with opposing views and take advantage of different thoughts as optimally as possible."
- c. To enable people participate in the decision making process, especially in the political arena.
- d. To make individuals' opinion heard which is made possible with the large increase in internet use.

Proponents of the above submission found out that there was a problem which resulted in conflicts on the internet and social media leading to fights and unpleasant acts.

The digital age is believed to have redefined the concept of freedom of expression. Digital realities transcend the limitations of time and space, thereby creating another world in virtual space where freedom of expression knows no bounds. According to Carlsson & Weibull (2018):

Freedom of expression, in both speech and text has never been greater than it is today. Digitisation has introduced new platforms for communication, which represents a host of opportunities for freedom of expression. The Public Sphere has been democratised, which has an enormous potential to enrich public debate. But the new technologies also imply problems, not least with regards to the limits of freedom of expression.

The “gateless” nature of the democratised public sphere has made individuals throw caution to the winds in the exercise of their rights to freedom of expression. Media online comedy skits have introduced a new trend in the way individuals exercise their rights to freedom of expression using online media platforms. Studies have shown that dilemmas arise whenever a hallowed right such as freedom of expression encounters revolutionary technology innovation, which digitisation implies (Ellul, 1964; Winston, 1998; Hirschfeldt, 2016 & Von Sydow, 2016).

Mark (2024) examined social media *and the Form and Content of Nigerian Comic Skits*, he used qualitative study to examine the comic skits of Nigerian comedians through netnography of skits by Taaoma, Mark Angel, Sabinus and Bello Galadanchi. His findings showed that Skits address themes such as gender roles, colonial legacies, social inequality, religion, corruption, in short (51s–4 min) slapstick/pidgin-based formats. Visual cues (cross-dressing, multi-role acting) enhance critique; subtitles extend reach. He concluded that skits are powerful tools of resistance and critique in a postcolonial setting and recommended similar analyses across platforms and deeper investigations into viewer reception. Mark (2024) strongly aligns with the current study because it focuses on skits as vehicles for cultural critique and expression (freedom of expression), echoing the researcher’s interest in comedy as guarantee of expression

Also, Ogba (2021) examined *Humour as a Sensitisation Tool in Nigerian Comedy Skits about Covid-19*, popular Covid-19 skits were purposively sampled through interpreted via Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM). He finds out that humorous messaging effectively challenges conspiracy theories and increases adherence to health protocols. Skits reached audiences with low government trust. The study concluded that skits functioned as credible, engaging public health communicators and recommended integration of skits into government risk communication strategies. Ogba (2021) demonstrated comedy’s as an instrumental role in exercising freedom of expression to influence public behavior which suggests another dimension for the current study.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on two theories; the libertarian theory of the press and the public sphere theory. The libertarian theory finds expression in the works of John Milton's "Areopagetica" published in 1644. According to Siebert *et al* (1956, pp.44-45):

Milton was confident that truth was definite and demonstrable and that it had unique powers of survival when permitted to assert itself in a free and open encounter.

In the above submission, Milton recognised that the right of free discussion might be limited but he avoided any general principles on which these limitations might be based. He wanted freedom from government censorship for serious-minded men who held honest, but differing opinions. Situating this theory within the context of this study, the right to have access to information and records of public interest should be a right to all and with that truth will compete favourably with falsehood in the media (which in this study is seen as that free marketplace of idea).

The concept of public sphere as theorised by the German Scholar, Jurgen Habermas directs attention to the historical evolution of the democratic role of the press. The public sphere, according to Habermas, is a space between the economy and the state providing an autonomous and open forum for public debate. Access to the space is free and freedom of association and assembly is guaranteed (Graham 1986, McQuail, 2010). The basic principles underlying the constitution and functioning of public sphere include general accessibility, especially to information, the elimination of privilege and the search for general norms and their rational legitimacy.

From the developed to the developing countries, many believe that the Internet, cell phones, face book, Twitter, WhatsApp and other social networking platforms act as the magic wands to revitalise deliberative and participatory democracy, due to social media's abilities to remove the filters which encumber participatory political communication through the "mainstream media" of newspaper, magazine, radio and television. Situating it in this study, online media comedy skits serve as a platform for public discourse where individuals make their opinion known in a satirical manner about attitudes and behaviours of public office holders and other important dignitaries in the country.

Methodology

Quantitative research design was adopted for this study with survey research as the method. The instrument adopted for the study is the questionnaire. The population consists of film and media scholars, social media content creators, lawyers and students of mass communication, film and multimedia studies. These are people who are knowledgeable about the nuances of communication management, ethics as well as media laws. Source from Association of Communication Scholars and Professional of Nigeria, Nigeria Bar Association, active social media users which amount to 1-2%

content creators and student of mass communications of 3 major university in Nigeria for the population which is 232,532. Taro Yamane's formula was used to determine 400 respondents by the researchers to ensure that only those with adequate knowledge of Nigeria's culture industry, social media and the law participated in the survey. Snowball sampling procedure was used as a technique to track the respondents who are spread across the country. Implicatively, a Google questionnaire was designed and sent to some of the respondents known to the researchers and solicited their help locating those known to them.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Extent Online Comedy Skits Enhance Freedom of Expression in Nigeria

Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Not censored by regulatory bodies in Nigeria	36 [9%]	139[34.8%]	181 [45.3%]	42 [10.5%]	2 [0.5%]
Not restrictive in their choice of language or fashion style	222[55.5%]	96[24%]	13[3.3%]	34 [8.5%]	35[8.8%]
comment on events that the mainstream media avoid	78 [19.5%]	176 [44%]	24 [6%]	57 [14.3%]	65[16.3%]
They satirise society in ways capable of causing a revolution	42[10.5%]	59 [14.8%]	127 [31.8%]	134 [33.5%]	38 [9.5%]
Through jokes they are able to draw attention to salient issues in the society.	256 [64%]	19 [4.8%]	0	61 [15.3%]	64 [16%]
Nigerians are able to contribute to discussions in the	101 [25.3%]	228 [57%]	19 [4.8%]	29 [7.3%]	23 [5.8%]

comment section
 thereby giving a
 voice to the
 voiceless.

The data in table 1 is used to measure the extent online comedy skits enhance freedom of expression in Nigeria. The response to the first statement on the table shows that a significant majority (45.3%) of the respondents cannot say if the Nigerian government censor social media/online contents. Although, a high percentage (34.8%) of the respondents agree that the government does not censor what appears on social media.

The second item in table 1 reveals that comedy skit makers are not restrictive in their choice of language or fashion style. The results show that 55.5% and 24% strongly agree and agree respectively with this statement. This implies that the freedom of online skit makers extends to word usage and dress patterns meaning that no regulates what skit makers wear, or say and how they say them.

Again, a significant majority of the respondents (44%) agree that online skit makers comment on events that the mainstream media avoid. In other words, online skit makers are not bound by the regulatory bottlenecks that shape mainstream media activities. Although, 31.8% of the respondents were neutral, 33.5% disagree with the statement that online comedy skit makers “satirize society in ways capable of causing a revolution”. What this shows is that while it’s agreed that online skit makers have the freedom to create contents that mimics or critical of the government, those contents are not sufficient to cause a revolution in Nigeria.

The data also revealed that 64% of the respondents strongly believe that, through jokes online comedy skit makers are able to draw attention to salient issues in the society. In other words, online comedy skits are able to mirror the society and set agenda on what is important in the society. A significant majority (82.3%) believe that citizens“are able to contribute to discussions in the comment section thereby giving a voice to the voiceless.” This signifies that online skits provide a platform for people to contribute to issues and events happening in their society or government.

Table 2: Extent of Freedom of Expression in Nigeria

Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Freedom of expression exists in Nigeria to a large extent	13 [3.3%]	84[21%]	102 [25.5%]	117 [29.3%]	84 [21%]
The media in Nigeria are free to criticise the	40 [10%]	119 [29.8%]	64 [16%]	106 [26.5%]	71 [17.8%]

government without fear					
No one in Nigeria has been harassed by government forces in the last five years for speaking against the government in the mainstream media	9 [2.3%]	26 [6.5%]	112 [28%]	183 [45.8%]	70 [17.5%]
Safety of media workers and social media skit makers are guaranteed.	6 [1.5%]	32 [8%]	141 [35.3%]	129 [32.3%]	92 [23%]

The first statement in table 2 shows that 50.3% of the 400 respondents do not believe that freedom of expression exists in Nigeria to a large extent. However, 25.5% were neutral. The fact that 21% and 3.3% respectively gave positive response is a sign that there is a measure of freedom of expression in Nigeria, however, such freedom is may not be adequate for a democratic society.

Majority (44.3%) of the respondents do not agree that the media in Nigeria are free to criticise the government without fear. Although, 39.8% believe that the media operates without fear of government harassment. Just like in Table 1 above, this reveals that the level of freedom allowed the media to operate still puzzles the citizens. Although, 28% were neutral, a significant majority (63.3%) of the respondents rejected the statement that “no one in Nigeria has been harassed by government forces in the last five years for speaking against the government in the mainstream media.” In other words, this evidences government’s intolerance for criticism and freedom of speech. Likewise, 35.3% cannot say if safety of media workers and social media skit makers are guaranteed in Nigeria. However, 55.3% signifying majority rejected the statement, implying that safety of media workers and social media skit makers are not guaranteed.

Discussion of Findings

One argument in favour of the social media is their democratic orientation which favours integration, collaboration, active participation and community engagement. Although, freedom of speech or of the press is not absolute anywhere, social media provides an enabling platform where participants interact on equal basis without an air of restrictions. However, the argument in some media quarters that the media in Nigeria, irrespective of the nature of the media or content, are not free, necessitated the desire to interrogate the extent of freedom enjoyed by those engaged in online comedy skits. The data in table 1

was utilised for this exercise. A total of 82.3% of the respondents believe that citizens “are able to contribute to discussions in the comment section of an online skit, thereby giving a voice to the voiceless.” This signifies that online skits provide a platform for people to contribute to issues and events in their society thereby deepening democracy. Supporting this view, Omolola (2020, p. 34) maintains that going by the “classical liberalism paradigm through the machineries of new and social media, agenda setting and status conferral are no longer the exclusive role of the traditional media.”

Furthermore, the results indicate that among others, opinions are divided on whether Nigerian government censor social media/online contents. For instance, while a significant majority (45.3%) of the respondents could not say if the Nigerian government censor social media/online contents, 34.8% agree that the government does not censor what appears on social media. Again, online skit makers are not bound by the regulatory bottlenecks that shape mainstream media activities. A significant majority of the respondents [44%] agree that online skit makers comment on events that the mainstream media avoid.

The results also showed that comedy skit makers are not restrictive in their choice of language or fashion style. According to the data, 55.5% and 24% of the respondents strongly agree and agree respectively with this statement. While this exemplifies freedom, it also has a lot of implications. Example, it means that society allows defamatory materials, obscenities, vulgar language, indecent exposure to thrive online. Cyber stalking, bullying, fake news, with its numerous disadvantages also thrive online. A typical example is the case of the lady that was interviewed on YanBaba’s online comedy show. She said that “she is an *ashawo* (whore), she sells her body to only married men because they pay more. To justify her trade, she added that she is from a polygamous home, meaning that her mother was her father’s side-chic (mistress before marriage). She would sleep with any man as long as the pay was good. It attracted a lot of funny reactions and the host would make a lot of money at the expense of the values of the society. Okafor, Onyike, Chiaha & Daniel (2013) citing educause.edu website notes that social media contents has the potential to “implicitly validate content that might be inaccurate, offensive, or otherwise lack credibility.”

The extent of freedom of expression in Nigeria directly impacts the freedom enjoyed by the media, including online skit makers. Nigeria's political and social climate often restricts freedom of expression, particularly for those who critique the government or societal norms. Evidently, the responses to the first statement in table 2 shows that 50.3% of the 400 respondents do not believe that freedom of expression exists in Nigeria to a large extent. More so, 44.3% do not believe that the media in Nigeria are free to criticise the government without fear. Although, 39.8% believe that the media operates without fear of government harassment. Just like in table 1 above, this reveals that the level of freedom allowed the media to operate still puzzles a lot of the citizens.

This research proves that media workers have been harassed in the past five years. This supports the findings by scholars like Popoola & Azeez (2015); Ogundoyin (2020)

and Hadiza & Binta (2021). Popoola & Azeez (2015, p.28) reveal that “62 journalists were killed between 2006 and 2012.” The International News Safety cited in Popoola & Azeez (2015, p.28) explains that “journalists continue to die because they dare to shine light on the darkest corners of societies.” In consonance, the results in table 2 further show that 35.3% can’t say if safety of media workers and social media skit makers are guaranteed in Nigeria. However, 55.3% signifying majority rejected the statement, implying that safety of media workers and social media skit makers are not guaranteed. Hadiza & Binta (2021) observed that greater part of the members (NUJ in Kano) had encountered dangers, assaults, disturbances, minimisation and segregation. The problem with the numerous assaults on media workers is that the more limited the freedom of expression in Nigeria, the more challenging it becomes for online comedy skit makers to create and share their content without fear of consequences, hindering their artistic and comedic freedom.

Conclusion

Based on the results, the researchers conclude that online content creators /skit makers use humor to comment on political, cultural or social issues. This makes them vulnerable to censorship or persecution, in a way, but, they still enjoy a level of freedom of expression that the traditional media is yet to attain. Government regulations, like the Cybercrimes Act and ban on Twitter, were the direct consequences of bloggers and skit makers’ involvement in matters affecting politics and governance. This notwithstanding, online skits provide a platform for people to contribute to issues and events in their society thereby deepening democracy. Thus, citizens are able to contribute to discussions in the comment section of an online skit, thereby giving a voice to the voiceless majority.

There is no agreement as to whether the Nigerian government censor social media/online contents. But, majority of the respondents were unequivocal in stating that online skit makers are not bound by the regulatory bottlenecks that shape mainstream media activities in Nigeria. Except in adherence to regulations associated with participation in any social network, comedy skit makers are not restrictive in their choice of language or fashion style. Personal observations show that they revert to local language by bypass sanctions. Thus, the following recommendations are hereby given:

1. Promote media literacy programs to help the public discern between satire and misinformation, fostering a more tolerant environment for comedy. At the same time, encourage social media platforms to uphold freedom of expression while combating hate speech and misinformation, ensuring online comedians' content remains accessible.
2. Government should encourage an independent and free media that can report on issues related to government interference in filmmaking without fear. Additionally, campaigns can be launched to raise awareness about the importance of freedom of

expression and comedy in fostering open, democratic discourse, fostering a more accepting atmosphere for comedy skit makers.

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